

The Effect of Addition of Young Coconut Water (*Cocos nucifera*) on Glutamate Content of White Oyster Mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus*)

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MSG (Monosodium Glutamate) or Vetsin is a food additive (BTP) which is used as a flavor enhancer in processed foods. This material is added in food preparations during the cooking process (Kadaryati *et al*, 2019). However, according to several studies that have been conducted reveal that there are various effects of using MSG. As according to Septadina (2014), MSG can cause abnormalities in human organs including the reproductive system which can cause infertility. In addition, the process of making MSG is also quite complicated, which needs to go through a process of fermentation, purification and crystallization (EFSA Panel on Food Additives and Nutrient Source Added to Food) (Kardayati *et al*, 2019). So this is the background to study the effect of adding young coconut water to increase the glutamic acid content in white oyster mushrooms as an alternative natural flavoring. Where this is closely related to the fields of microbiology and biochemistry.

White oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) is a wood fungus that grows sideways on rotting wood trunks. This mushroom has a fruiting body that grows to resemble shells (oysters). The mushroom body has a hood (pileus) and a stalk (stipe/stalk). Pileus is shaped like an oyster shell measuring 5-15 cm and the white part of the oyster mushroom is wavy (Mufarrihah, 2009). Oyster mushrooms can be a solution as a safe natural flavoring because it contains glutamic acid which is low in sodium and potassium (Ningsih, 2018). Oyster mushrooms contain protein in the fruit body. This protein can trigger protease activity in the body fruit. Protease are break down proteins into short peptides and soluble amino acids. In the protein content of white oyster mushrooms about 10.5-30.4% in every 100 grams fruit body weight (Periadi *et al*, 2015). The fresh fruiting body of the oyster mushroom contains about 90% moisture. It has a source of crude protein which is 37%, crude fiber is 21.97%, ash is 6.87%, calcium is 607 mg and manganese is 136 mg. Based on the high protein content, oyster mushrooms can be used as a natural flavoring agent (Asngad, 2021). The content of glutamic acid in oyster mushrooms is 21.70 mg/g dry weight (Samaun, 2021). However, the glutamate content in oyster mushrooms is still relatively low compared to MSG which contains 78% glutamate, which means that 1 MSG salt contains 0.78 glutamate. So it is necessary to find a solution to increase the glutamate content in white oyster mushrooms.

The addition of young coconut water to the growth medium of white oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) is thought to increase the umami or glutamic acid content in white oyster mushrooms. Media mushrooms growing is one factor determinant of fungal growth. Therefore, mushrooms need additional nutrition to support growth other than that in sawdust (Periadi *et al*, 2016) It is known that in coconut water there is glutamic acid which is naturally available, not synthesized so that there are no contaminants and have a negative impact on the human body. As according to Yuwono (2015), coconut water contains 14.50% of the amino acid glutamate. Coconut water contains vitamins B1, B12, phosphorus, nitrogen and carbohydrates which can be used as additional nutrients for mushrooms (Nurmiati *et al*, 2014). Coconut water also contains two natural growth hormones, namely auxins and cytokinins. In the metabolic process, it is suspected that cytokinins have an important role in protein synthesis (Tandirerung *et al*, 2021). The amount of umami material in mushrooms is influenced by many factors including the type of species, stage of maturity, part of the fungus (pileus and stipe), quality level and storage time, all of which are closely related to the growth of the fungus itself.

Based on research by Tandirerung (2021), the interaction between coconut water as PGR and mushroom growing media gave the best effect on body weight of fresh white oyster mushrooms. This is because the provision of coconut water containing auxins and cytokinins can be used as a source of energy in growth and stimulate cell division so as to increase the body weight of the mushroom fruit and have the ability to encourage cell division and tissue differentiation. Based on Shifriyah's research (2012), increasing the production of white oyster mushrooms is done by increasing it through the provision of potential nutrients, namely by adding old coconut water. The addition of coconut water is done by injecting it on the surface of the baglog (growing medium) which is in contact with the air and is carried out periodically so that an improvement in growth is obtained by increasing the average width of the white oyster mushroom hood. So this confirms that the addition of coconut water as a growth nutrient correlates with an increase in glutamic acid content in white oyster mushrooms (*Pleurotus ostreatus*). As according to Alamsjah (2017), the requirements for microorganism growth media are: (1) having nutrients that are easy to use by microorganisms; (2) have the appropriate osmotic pressure, surface tension and pH; (3) does not contain substances that inhibit the growth of the desired microorganism; (4) sterile and protected from contamination.

So that white oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) which contains glutamic acid with low sodium and potassium content can be used as a natural flavoring. However, the glutamic acid content in this mushroom is still considered low so it is necessary to make efforts to increase the glutamic acid content so that it can be a substitute for synthetic flavoring. Increasing the glutamic acid content in white oyster

mushrooms can be done by adding coconut water which contains glutamic acid and various growth nutrients in white oyster mushroom growing media. So that it can be obtained oyster mushrooms which contain glutamic acid which is equivalent to synthetic flavoring, so that it can be used as a natural and healthier flavoring.

REFERENCES

- Alamsjah, Feskaharny. (2017). Pengaruh Media Sintetik yang Berbeda Terhadap Pertumbuhan Miselium Fungi Ektomikoriza *Cenococcum sp.* *PROSISDING SEMINAR NASIONAL BIOLOGI XXIV PBI MANADO*, 35-39.
- Asngad, A. (2021). Kualitas Penyedap Rasa Alami Dalam Bentuk Cair Dari Kombinasi Berbagai Jamur Edibel Dengan Penambahan Variasi Glukosa. *Bioeksperimen*, 7 (1).
- Kardayati, S. Margaretha A. & Yuni A. (2019). Formulasi dan Uji Sensori Produk Bumbu Penyedap Berbasis Jamur Tiram Putih (*Pleurotus ostreatus*). *agriTECH*, 41 (3).
- Mufarrihah, L. (2009). Pengaruh Penambahan Bekatul Dan Ampas Tahu Pada Media Terhadap Pertumbuhan Produksi Jamur Tiram Putih (*Pleurotus ostreatus*). *Skripsi*. Jurusan Biologi. Universitas Islam Negeri Malang.
- Ningsih, I.Y., Ika B.S. & Ema R. (2018). Pengembangan Produk Penyedap Rasa dan Tepung Jamur tiram di Desa Penambangan dan Kelurahan Debasah Kabupaten Bandowoso. *Warta Pengabdian*, 12(3), 307-308. dan Air Beras Sebagai Alternatif PElapukan Media Terhadap PErtumbuhan Jamur Tiram Kelabu (*Pleurotus sajor caju* (Fries) Singer). *Jurnal Biologi Universitas Andalas*, 3(3): 224-248.
- Nurmiati, N., Merisya & Periadnadi. (2014). Pengaruh Pengemasan Air Kelapa Periadnadi, P., Nurmiati & Imelda. (2015). Pengaruh Pencucuan Media Serbuk Gergaji Terhadap Keberadaan dan Aktivitas Beberapa Enzim Media dan Tubuh Buah Jamur Tiram Putih. *Online Journal Natural Science*, 4(3), 310-3021.
- Periadnadi, P., Nurmiati & Risyah, P. (2016). The Effect of Calcite and Dolomit to Mycelium Growth and Production of Pink Oyster Mushroom (*Pleurotus flabellatus* Saccardo). *Online Journal Natural Science*, 5(1):1-10.
- Samaun, S. (2021). Pembuatan Penyedap rasa instan Berbahan Dasar Tomat dengan Penambahan Jamur Tiram. *Journal of agritech Science*. Volume 5(2).
- Septadina, I., S. (2014). Pengaruh Monosodium Glutamat Terhadap Sistem Reproduksi. *Seminar Bagian Anatomi*, 1-12.

- Shifriyah, A., kaswan B. & Sinar S. (2012). Pertumbuhan dan Produksi Jamur Tiram Putih (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) Pada Penambahan Dua Sumber Nutrisi. *AGROVIGOR*, 5(1), 8-12.
- Tandirerung, W.Y., Berlian Z.Y. & Yustin A. (2021). Respon Produksi Jamur Tiram Putih (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) terhadap Penggunaan Limbah Daun kakao Sebagai Media tumbuh dan ZPT Air Kelapa. *Jurnal Ilmiah Agrosains*, 12(1),48-51.
- Yuwono, S., S. 2015. *Air Kelapa Muda*. darsatop.lecture.ub.ac.id. Diakses 19 Maret 2022.